

THE ROLE OF THE WORKS OF ABDULLA AVLONI IN THE EDUCATION OF THE YOUNGER GENERATION

Jumayeva Sarvinoz Faxriddin kizi

TerSPI theory and methodology of Education and training

(Primary Education) specialty 2-year graduate

E-mail: sarvinozjumayeva0518@gmail.com

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Abstract: This article talks about the importance of the great enlightener Abdulla Avloni's works in the moral education of elementary school students.

Key words: morality, education, enlightenment, patriotism, hard work, spiritual and cultural heritage, good behavior, bad behavior.

One of the peculiarities of the current era is that the problem of youth education has become an urgent issue. Another of the peculiarities of the era of globalization is the aggravation of the problems of moral and spiritual education, the issue of raising young people covers all aspects of social, economic life. Therefore, in the minds of students, their upbringing in the spirit of finding a positive solution to the problem of a new content of umiminsonic and national culture, its spiritual and moral principles, a responsible approach to social life, the formation of concepts related to the spiritual enrichment of our society is considered an important socio-pedagogical task.

The rich spiritual and cultural heritage, national values of the Uzbek people are of great importance in the upbringing of the highest human qualities in the growing generation. From eastern including, Central Asian alloms occupy a special place among national values according to their scientific views, pedagogical (educational) skill, which ensured the development of World Science. The use of patriotic, humanistic, hard work, responsiveness, modesty views put forward by them and for centuries in young people is considered an important ideological basis for the fact that even today there is a high moral culture. The study of our national heritage is the most important support that develops work in the field of education today.

The great thinkers and allomas of the East themselves, who have focused their entire creative activities on the formation and development of the moral and spiritual culture of the individual. It is with this feature that the creative activities of Eastern thinkers differ from those of Western thinkers.

In his work " Turkiy guliston yohud axloq", the great enlightener Abdulla Avlani says that morality is "a science that calls men for good, and discourages them from evil". It is in this resource that provides information about morality, its social significance that alloma touches on good and bad behavior. In the theory of the defect of alloma, good manners are: fatonat (mind), Dionate (faith), nazofat (purity and purity), zeal, math (works of merit), contentment, healing, science, patience, hilm (soft nature) discipline, the norm of lust, conscience, to lean the Fatherland, truth, theoretical lesson, chastity, pride, perception and intelligence, hifzi lison (language and literature), economics, vigor (nature), love, forgiveness).

He also reflects on the role of child-rearing: "if a man grew up in his youth to be gullible, uneducated, immoral, to expect good from such men, to stand on the ground and reach out to

the stars". In his opinion, the social environment, family conditions and people around children are important about the composition of moral qualities in children. In the history of Uzbek pedagogy, they described Avloni as the first "Pedagogy", that is, the science of child education. Avloni divides the upbringing of a child into 4 sections in relative terms:

1. The time of upbringing.
2. Physical education.
3. Thought education.
4. Reflects on the education of morality and its importance.

In the section "Tarbiyaning zamoni", the need to give upbringing from youth emphasizes that everyone should get into this: parents, teachers, government and others. Avloni, upbringing is not a private business, it is a national social work. "Alhosil argues that nurture is either a matter of life or of life or of salvation or of destruction or of happiness or of disaster for us". The progress of each people, the power of the state, depends in many ways on the upbringing of generations, adib argues.

Upbringing begins with the birth of offspring and continues until the end of life. It will consist of several stages – home, kindergarten, school and community education. Avloni understands the scope of upbringing in a broad sense. It does not limit it to a single morality. He first reassures that it is necessary to take care of the health of the child. The work "Turkiy guliston yoxud axloq" promotes the ideas of the Enlightenment. Adib says of Science in the book: "Science is the glory of the world, the good of the hereafter. Knowledge is a Supreme, sacred virtue for man. Also, says that science shows us our condition, our action, like a game". To serve in the way of the development of our country, which is going through a period of development, it has become a necessity today to educate young people with a strong spiritual faith and one of the issues that our state is in the spotlight. On the basis of the creative heritage of Abdullah Avloni, love and loyalty to the motherland, moral attitude to work, moral approach to their surroundings, as well as the attitude of each student to himself and his personal behavior serve as a valuable resource in finding a decision.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2018-yil 14-avgustdagi "Yoshlarni ma'naviy-axloqiy va jismoniy barkamol etib tarbiyalash, ularga ta'lim-tarbiya berish tizimini sifat jihatidan yangi bosqichga ko'tarish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi PQ-3907 qarori // <https://lex.uz/docs/-3864155>
2. Abdulla Avloniy. Turkiy guliston yoxud axloq - Toshkent: Yoshlar nashriyot uyi, 2019. - 96 bet.